

Effect of Substrate and Thermal Treatments on MOCVD-grown Sb₂Te₃ Thin Films

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ABSTRACT: Antimony telluride (Sb₂Te₃) thin films were obtained by Metallorganic Chemical Vapor Deposition. The films were grown on the crystalline Si(100), Al₂O₃(0001) and the amorphous SiO₂, α-Al₂O₃ substrates. Their structural properties were compared with the Sb₂Te₃/Si(111) heterostructure. In addition to the effect of the substrate, the influence of pre- and post-growth thermal annealings is also presented. The quality of the films is discussed by comparing their morphological properties, such as roughness and granularity, and ascertaining their crystallinity and their in-plane and out-of-plane orientation.

KEYWORDS: Metallorganic Chemical Vapor Deposition, Topological Insulator, Antimony Telluride, Thin Film, Epitaxy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Chalcogenide materials are currently foreseen to find application in the development of emerging technologies. In particular, chalcogenide structures, such as Sb₂Te₃, Bi₂Te₃, or Bi₂Se₃, have recently been emphasized as topological insulators,[1-5] exploited in phase-change memories,[6, 7] thermoelectric devices,[8, 9] and spintronics.[10]

Either as thin films or in the form of more engineered structures like nanowires[11-13] and multilayer stacks,[14-17] the deposition of tellurides and selenides has been achieved by both physical and chemical methods.[18-26] Amongst these, Metallorganic Chemical Vapor Deposition (MOCVD), a large-scale and industrially-ready technique, is capable of fabricating high-quality materials.

Recently, taking advantage of the reactivity of SbCl₃ (antimony chloride) and Te(SiMe₃)₂ (bis(trimethylsilyl)telluride),[1, 27] their use as precursors in a room temperature MOCVD process to grow Sb₂Te₃ thin films on Si(111) has been proven.[28]

In view of the integration of Sb_2Te_3 -based components on electronic devices, it is pivotal studying their growth behaviour on substrates other than Si(111), and specifically on both crystalline and amorphous substrates, including oxides (for instance to allow back-gating). From an application perspective, achieving highly oriented films is mandatory: a controlled out-of-plane orientation – i.e., a c-oriented Sb_2Te_3 thin film or even the ability to attain an epitaxial growth – are essential pre-requisites to best exploit their physical properties as topological insulators.

So far, the growth of Sb_2Te_3 has been demonstrated by molecular beam epitaxy on Si(111) and BaF_2 , [23, 29, 30] pulsed laser deposition on Si(111), [31] thermal evaporation on $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$, [32] and MOCVD on Si(111), as well as on ZnTe buffer layers. [28, 33]

Here, we report our recent investigation on the deposition of Sb_2Te_3 thin films by room temperature MOCVD. We focused on the morphological and structural changes induced by pre- and post-growth thermal annealing and on the effect of the substrate, ultimately identifying highly oriented crystalline Sb_2Te_3 , and conducted RT resistivity measurements to functionally characterize a structurally broad set of thin films.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Si(111), Si(100), and SiO_2 (nominal 50 nm thermal oxide on Si(100)) wafers were acquired from Silicon Materials Inc. and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$ from CrysTec GmbH. Amorphous Al_2O_3 ($\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$) thin films (thickness of ca. 10 nm) were prepared by atomic layer deposition on SiO_2 (nominal 50 nm thermal oxide on Si(100)) in a Savannah 200 reactor using TMA-(trimethylaluminium) and H_2O as aluminium and oxygen source, respectively; the deposition was carried out at 150 °C, according to the following parameters: TMA pulse time: 0.05 s, TMA purge time: 45 s, H_2O pulse time: 0.2 s, H_2O purge time: 45 s, number of cycles: 100. Substrates were cut in approximately 1 to 2 cm^2 pieces.

2.2 Sb_2Te_3 Thin Films by MOCVD

Prior to deposition, the Si(111) and Si(100) substrates were treated with hydrofluoric acid (5% in deionized water) for 3 min, thoroughly rinsed with deionized H_2O , and N_2 -dried; the $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ substrates were freshly prepared prior to MOCVD growth. After preparation, substrates were quickly transferred into the glovebox-protected MOCVD chamber. Sb_2Te_3 thin films were grown with an Aixtron AIX 200/4 MOCVD tool, equipped with an IR-heated 4" rotating graphite susceptor. Electronic grade MOCVD precursors SbCl_3 and $\text{Te}(\text{SiMe}_3)_2$ were provided by Air Liquide Electronics. Precursors were contained into bubblers thermalized at 20.0 ± 0.1 °C and delivered to the MOCVD chamber through the vapor-saturated ultra-pure N_2 carrier gas. Depositions were carried out for 90 min at 25 °C and 15 mbar pressure, with a total flow of 5.575 l/min, and setting the vapour pressure of SbCl_3 and $\text{Te}(\text{SiMe}_3)_2$ at 2.28 and $3.32 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mbar, respectively. Substrates annealing (prior to deposition) was performed in situ for 60 min at 500 °C and 20 mbar, with a total N_2 flow of 11.000 l/min. Post-growth film annealing was performed in situ according to the following routine: 1) heating ramp: 5.575 l/min N_2 flow, 900 mbar, from room temperature (RT) to 300 °C in 10 min; 2) Annealing: 5.575 l/min N_2 flow, 900 mbar, 300 °C, 15 min; 3) Cooling ramp: 1.500 l/min

N₂ flow, 990 mbar, from 300 °C to 200 °C in 20 min, from 200 °C to 100 °C in 35 min, from 100 °C to 50 °C in 20 min.

2.3 Materials Characterization

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) images were acquired with a ZEISS Supra40 field emission scanning electron microscope operating at an acceleration voltage of 15 kV. Samples were cut and cross-section images collected at a tilting angle of 25°. Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) measurements were acquired on a Bruker Dimension Edge instrument in non-contact mode using AFM silicon probes (TESPA, Bruker). The surface roughness is expressed as Root Mean Square Roughness (RMS Roughness, R_q). Total Reflection X-Ray Fluorescence (TXRF) measurements were performed using an X-ray total reflection spectrometer equipped with a Mo K_α radiation source. Elemental compositions were obtained from the ratio of the antimony and tellurium L_α lines (Sb L_α = 3.604 keV; Te L_α = 3.768 keV). X-Ray Reflectivity (XRR) and X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) patterns were acquired with a HRXRD IS2000 diffractometer equipped with a Cu K_α radiation source, a four-circle goniometer, and a curved 120° position-sensitive detector. Electrical resistivity (ρ) was measured with a custom-made four points Van der Pauw setup in vacuum (base pressure = 10⁻⁵ mbar), on 1 × 1 cm² samples. Intrinsic substrates (with $\rho > 10000 \Omega\cdot\text{cm}$) were used for electrical measurements of the Sb₂Te₃ films grown on crystalline silicon.

3. RESULTS and DISCUSSION

To establish the effect of the substrate in directing the MOCVD of Sb₂Te₃ thin films we explored the use of crystalline and amorphous substrates. Amongst these, sapphire has recently been found suitable for good quality and highly crystalline telluride thin film preparation by thermal evaporation,[32] whereas SiO₂ has been used to successfully produce out-of-plane oriented Sb₂Te₃ films by sputtering.[34]

Taking advantage of the optimization achieved in the growth of Sb₂Te₃ by MOCVD on Si(111),[28] in addition to the substrate assessment, we examined the effect of thermal treatments on the bare substrates (substrate annealing prior to deposition) and on the deposited thin films (post-growth annealing).

The chemical reactivity of SbCl₃ and Te(SiMe₃)₂ allowed exploiting the RT antimony telluride deposition, rather than a high-temperature pyrolysis-driven process; it is worth mentioning that the same set of precursors could be used in a high-temperature MOCVD: varying the temperature of the growth, within the 100 - 250 °C range, changes were induced on the granularity and overall morphology of the films (Fig. S1 of supplementary material).[27] Nevertheless, the best quality was achieved via room temperature MOCVD growth implementing the substrates annealing and the post-growth annealing steps.

Under the adopted RT experimental conditions, that consisted of SbCl₃ and Te(SiMe₃)₂ partial pressures set to 2.23 × 10⁻⁴ and 3.25 × 10⁻⁴ mbar, respectively, a total flow of 5.575 l min⁻¹, and a chamber pressure of 15 mbar, the process yielded, at a deposition time of 90 min, films in the thickness range from 29 to 35 nm, depending on the substrate of choice. As a general trend, a slight thickness reduction was observed on the films subjected to the annealing processes (see Table 1).

The stoichiometry of the films, probed by Total Reflection X-Ray Fluorescence spectroscopy, was constantly found to be Sb_{2.0}Te_{3.0} regardless of the substrate or the thermal annealing.

Table 1. Sb₂Te₃ root mean square roughness (R_q, nm), measured by AFM and XRR, and thickness (nm), determined by XRR.

Substrates	As Deposited			Substrate Annealing			Post-Growth Annealing		
	R _q (AFM)	R _q (XRR)	Thickness (XRR)	R _q (AFM)	R _q (XRR)	Thickness (XRR)	R _q (AFM)	R _q (XRR)	Thickness (XRR)
Si(111) ^a	3.88	3.1	33.7	1.81	2.0	32.5	1.32	1.5	32.0
Si(100)	4.80	4.6	33.7	2.78	3.4	31.0	2.26	2.6	31.7
SiO ₂	2.41	3.1 ^b	35.0 ^c	4.90	6.6	30.9	5.51	4.5	32.4
a-Al ₂ O ₃	3.40	3.3 ^d	32.2	3.61	4.1 ^e	29.0	3.07	3.4 ^f	27.5
Al ₂ O ₃ (0001)	1.94	2.6	28.8	3.25	3.9 ^g	28.2 ^h	2.18	3.3 ⁱ	25.2 ^j

^a Si(111) is reported for comparison purpose.[28] ^b Sb₂O₃ interlayer roughness: 0.4 nm. ^c Sb₂O₃ interlayer thickness: 2.0 nm. ^d a-Al₂O₃ roughness: 0.5 nm. ^e a-Al₂O₃ roughness: 0.4 nm. ^f a-Al₂O₃ roughness: 0.5 nm. ^g Sb₂O₃ interlayer roughness: 0.1 nm. ^h Sb₂O₃ interlayer thickness: 0.5 nm. ⁱ Sb₂O₃ interlayer roughness: 0.1 nm. ^j Sb₂O₃ interlayer thickness: 0.3 nm.

3.1 Sb₂Te₃ - As Deposited

The Sb₂Te₃ - As Deposited films (annealing not applied to these materials) were obtained with a pronounced granularity; however, when grown on SiO₂ and Al₂O₃(0001) they appeared appreciably smoother (Fig. 1). Their surface roughness (AFM R_q values of 2.41 nm and 1.94 nm for Sb₂Te₃/SiO₂ and Sb₂Te₃/Al₂O₃(0001), respectively) was significantly lower compared to the films deposited on other substrates (Table 1; Fig. S2 of supplementary material), including Sb₂Te₃/Si(111).[28]

XRR analyses confirmed the AFM roughness trend and indicated sapphire to favour the higher quality Sb₂Te₃ - As Deposited thin film —as inferred from the electronic density and surface roughness values. Noteworthy, an optimal XRR model of Sb₂Te₃/SiO₂ required a 2 nm Sb₂O₃ interlayer,[1] component not needed with the other films (Table 1; Fig. S3 of supplementary material).

Irrespective of the substrate used, the Sb₂Te₃ - As Deposited thin films had a relatively similar structural quality, as ascertained by the shape and position of the peaks in the grazing incidence X-ray diffractograms (Fig. 2).

However, the sharper and more intense (00 ℓ) peaks in Sb₂Te₃/a-Al₂O₃ and Sb₂Te₃/Al₂O₃(0001) indicated an overall higher crystallinity, as well as crystallites bigger in size and likely out-of-plane oriented along the [00 ℓ] direction. On the other hand, the more intense and broader 015 reflection in the diffraction patterns of Sb₂Te₃/Si(100) and Sb₂Te₃/SiO₂ revealed their greater random and polycrystalline nature and possibly amorphous fractions. The X-ray diffraction analysis in Bragg-Brentano geometry showed mostly the (00 ℓ) reflections only, further supporting that the Sb₂Te₃ films are mostly (00 ℓ) out-of-plane oriented. From the rocking curve around the (006) reflection of Sb₂Te₃/a-Al₂O₃, a mosaicity of approximately 4° was calculated. This value is lower than that measured on Sb₂Te₃/Si(111) (9°),[28] revealing a higher order of the (00 ℓ) crystallites. Nevertheless, the (00 ℓ) reflections are very weak, and their broadening along the ω

direction indicated a still high mosaicity (Fig. S4 of supplementary material). Further investigations found no presence of any in-plane order.

Fig. 1. Tilted cross-section SEM images of Sb₂Te₃ - As Deposited on (from left to right) Si(111), Si(100), SiO₂, Al₂O₃(0001), and a-Al₂O₃. Si(111) is reported for comparison purpose.[28]

Fig. 2. Grazing incidence X-ray diffraction pattern of Sb₂Te₃ - As Deposited on (black) SiO₂, (red) Si(100), (blue) a-Al₂O₃, and (green) Al₂O₃(0001).

3.2 Sb₂Te₃ - Substrate Annealing

Substrate annealing (i.e, pre-growth thermal annealing of substrates) was performed in situ at 500 °C and at a reduced pressure (20 mbar), whereas the subsequent MOCVD process was conducted at RT. The substrate annealing had a marked effect on the morphology of the films grown on all the tested substrates (Fig. 3). The granularity appreciably improved on the crystalline substrate Si(100), as also previously observed on Si(111),[28] resulting in a more continuous and uniform film with a lowered surface roughness (RMS R_q of 2.8 nm).

In contrast, the substrate annealing did not prove to be just as much effective on the two aluminium oxide substrates. Even though the grains cohesion was enhanced to such an extent that the films appeared continuous, clearly visible from the SEM observations (detailed in Fig. 3), their roughness instead worsened to 3.6 and 3.3 nm for $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3/\text{a-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$, respectively (Table 1).

On the other hand, the substrate annealing had a drastically reverse effect once applied to the SiO_2 substrate: the deposited Sb_2Te_3 material formed islands approximately 100 nm in size, so that it no longer does qualify as a film. XRR analyses outlined that, differently from the $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3/\text{SiO}_2$ - As Deposited film, the Sb_2O_3 interlayer was not present; in fact, the substrate annealing is expected to readily remove strongly adsorbed water and significantly reduce silanols —features accountable for the formation of the detected low-density layer (Table 1; Fig. S3 of supplementary material).

Modelling the $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$ XRR data, instead, a very thin (0.5 nm) interlayer, whose electronic density is compatible with the Sb_2O_3 chemical composition, has to be accounted for.

Roughness-wise, XRR measurements outlined that, except the $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3/\text{Si}$ case, the substrate annealing step unfavourably affected the growth of the films, particularly on SiO_2 .

The crystallinity appeared enhanced in all the films grown on annealed substrates, except SiO_2 . On the latter, the total absence of the (00ℓ) reflections indicated randomly oriented crystallites (Fig. 4) and the Bragg-Brentano analyses further confirmed the absence of an out-of-plane ordering due to randomly oriented crystallites (Fig. S5 of supplementary material) —a description well matching the clustering observed by SEM (Fig. 3).

The substrate annealing favoured a general out-of-plane orientation of the Sb_2Te_3 film along the $[00\ell]$ direction both on $\text{a-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$, as confirmed by the almost total absence of reflections pertaining to different crystalline planes (Fig. 4; Fig. S5 of supplementary material). However, the intensity ratio of the (003) and (006) reflections does not correspond to the one reported in database,[35] suggesting a different texturing and/or a non-optimal crystallization of the film.

Fig. 3. Tilted cross-section SEM images of Sb_2Te_3 - Substrate Annealing on (from left to right) $\text{Si}(111)$, $\text{Si}(100)$, SiO_2 , $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$, and $\text{a-Al}_2\text{O}_3$. $\text{Si}(111)$ is reported for comparison purpose.[28]

The $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3/\text{Si}(100)$ structure appeared as the most out-of-plane ordered: the high and sharp (00ℓ) peaks indicated larger crystallites (Fig. 4), whereas the presence of a faint but broadened (015) peak and further reflections not belonging to the (00ℓ) family of planes revealed a polycrystalline nature and amorphous fractions, features instead not observed in $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3/\text{Si}(111)$. An XRD scan of the azimuthal angle (Φ)

performed on the 015 reflection of the (00 l) out-of-plane oriented crystallites highlighted equally spaced peaks at $2\Theta = 28^\circ$, indicative of a certain degree of in-plane order (Fig. 5; Fig. S6 of supplementary material).

The three-fold symmetry of the rhombohedral Sb_2Te_3 cell would ideally provide three 60° -spaced peaks, as found in $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3/\text{Si}(111)$. The occurrence of six 30° -spaced peaks is therefore rationalized as two families of crystallites, whose 015 reflections are 30° offset in-plane.

Fig. 4. Grazing incidence X-ray diffraction pattern of Sb_2Te_3 - Substrate Annealing on (black) SiO_2 , (red) $\text{Si}(100)$, (blue) $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$, and (green) sapphire.

Fig. 5. XRD maps (left) in Bragg-Brentano geometry and (right) ϕ angle scans of Sb_2Te_3 - Substrate Annealing on $\text{Si}(100)$.

3.3 Sb_2Te_3 – Post-Growth Annealing

The quality of the Sb_2Te_3 thin films grown by room temperature MOCVD was effectively improved through a post-growth annealing.[28] We applied the same protocol on all the Sb_2Te_3 - Substrate Annealing films

and found that the surface roughness generally diminished – as probed by AFM and XRR analyses – to values as low as 2.2 nm and 2.3 nm on the crystalline $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$ and $\text{Si}(100)$ substrates, respectively (see Table 1; Fig. S3 of supplementary material). Interestingly, the XRR model of the $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$ heterostructure still evidenced an interlayer, thinner (0.3 nm) and denser than the one observed in the Substrate Annealing analogue, and suggestive of an intermixing between the Sb_2Te_3 film and the sapphire surface.

The thermal processing favoured the crystallization of the films: the SEM and AFM images (Fig. 6) highlight the high crystallinity and the extent of the film orientation.

In $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3/\text{SiO}_2$ - Post-Growth Annealing it is evident that the highly granular nature was retained – reflecting the granularity of the parent samples – but the isolated grains underwent a marked crystallization (Figs. 3 and 6).

The intensity and sharpness of the $(00l)$ peaks in the grazing incidence XRD patterns (Fig. 7) demonstrated an improved crystallinity, as result of a higher fraction of crystallites oriented along the $(00l)$ direction, except for the $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3/\text{SiO}_2$ thin film that was instead characterized by the (015) and (1010) reflections, thus revealing a polycrystalline component.

The combined XRD measurements in Bragg-Brentano geometry and the ϕ angle scans indicated that the films grown on the amorphous $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and SiO_2 were poorly oriented.

In fact, the peaks highly broadened along ω (Fig. 8) and the continuous and faint line detected at $2\theta = 28^\circ$ in the ϕ angle scans (Fig. S7) indicated only partially $(00l)$ out-of-plane oriented crystallites, with an almost random in-plane orientation. Therefore, the thermal treatment just induced a partial reorientation of the Sb_2Te_3 grains to form highly textured films along the out-of-plane $(00l)$ direction.

Fig. 6. (top) Tilted cross-section SEM images and (bottom) AFM views of Sb_2Te_3 - Post-Growth Annealing on (from left to right) $\text{Si}(111)$, $\text{Si}(100)$, SiO_2 , $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$, and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$. $\text{Si}(111)$ is shown for comparison purpose.[28]

Fig. 7. Grazing incidence X-ray diffraction pattern of Sb_2Te_3 – Post-Growth Annealing on (black) SiO_2 , (red) $\text{Si}(100)$, (blue) $\text{a-Al}_2\text{O}_3$, and (green) $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$.

Fig. 8. XRD maps in Bragg-Brentano geometry of Sb_2Te_3 - Post-Growth Annealing on $\text{Si}(100)$, SiO_2 , $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$, and $\text{a-Al}_2\text{O}_3$.

On the other hand, Sapphire and $\text{Si}(100)$ favoured a more ordered structure. In $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$, the rocking curve of the (006) reflection appeared very narrow, with a mosaicity of 0.15° , and most likely superimposed on a much broader, but extremely weak peak that could indicate an additional family of less out-of-plane oriented crystallites. The Bragg-Brentano XRD data of $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3/\text{Si}(100)$ revealed instead a mosaicity of approximately 1.5° (Fig. 9a).

$\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$ was characterized by three 60° -spaced peaks in the ϕ angle scan, typical of the symmetry of the rhombohedral Sb_2Te_3 crystalline structure (Fig. 9b); the lower intensity of the peak

positioned at $\phi = 90^\circ$ can be explained with the coexistence of two not equally populated families of Sb_2Te_3 crystals offset in-plane of 60° , as previously proposed.[36]

Fig. 9. a) Profiles of the (006) peak along ω extracted from the XRD measurements in Bragg-Brentano geometry and b) profiles of the ϕ angle scans of Sb_2Te_3 - Post-Growth Annealing on (left) $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$ and (right) $\text{Si}(100)$.

The ϕ angle scan, where $\Phi = 0^\circ$ corresponds to the direction parallel to $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3[110]$ (Fig. 9b), allowed to determine the epitaxial relationships between the Sb_2Te_3 - Post Growth Annealing film and the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$ substrate: these relations can be written as $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3[00\bar{l}] \parallel \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3[00\bar{l}]$ and $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3[015] \parallel \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3[110]$. The low mosaicity value, along with an in-plane ordering, supported the formation of an epitaxial Sb_2Te_3 film in $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$. Nevertheless, the epitaxy is corroborated by the relatively limited 10.7% mismatch between the film and substrate in-plane lattice parameters ($a_{\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3} = 4.25 \text{ nm}$ and $a_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(0001)} = 4.76 \text{ nm}$). In $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3/\text{Si}(100)$, instead, the mutual crystallographic orientations between the film and the substrate could not be straightforwardly identified. Consistently with its parent Substrate Annealing sample, the XRD ϕ angle scan showed six 30° -spaced peaks (Fig. 9b), suggesting two families of crystalline Sb_2Te_3 grains. One of these, linked to a ϕ angle spacing of 60° , was identified by the orientations $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3[00\bar{l}] \parallel \text{Si}(100)[100]$ and $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3[015] \parallel \text{Si}(100)[110]$, whereas the other one, while sharing the same out-of-plane orientation, was additionally rotated in-plane of 30° with respect to the $\text{Si}(100)[110]$ direction. As a result of commensurability considerations and given the two Sb_2Te_3 in-plane crystalline orientations, an epitaxy definition was not fully applicable. Moreover, the scattered intensity connecting the six 30° -spaced $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3/\text{Si}(100)$ reflections indicated a not negligible contribution from random in-plane orientations of the Sb_2Te_3 crystallites (Fig. 9b), causing in-plane structural disorder on the $\text{Si}(001)$ surface.

For a thorough description of the substrate effects on the Sb_2Te_3 growth, we would recall that the Sb_2Te_3 - Post-Growth Annealing on $\text{Si}(111)$, characterized by a mosaicity of 0.46° and an almost perfect in-plane

orientation, has been described by the epitaxial relationship $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3[00\bar{l}]\parallel\text{Si}[111]$ and $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3[015]\parallel\text{Si}[011]$. [28]

Therefore, the 3-fold symmetry of the Si(111) and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$ surfaces favors the formation of highly ordered Sb_2Te_3 crystallites, fixing their orientation in both the in-plane and out-of-plane directions.

3.4 Electrical Resistivity Measurements

The resistivity values of the Sb_2Te_3 films grown on all the different substrates, as obtained by the Van der Pauw method, are reported in Fig. 10 and Table 2.

The general trend over all the thin films indicated a decrease in resistivity from the As Deposited to the Post-Growth Annealing Sb_2Te_3 films (Fig. 10). Amongst the As Deposited films, lower resistivity was measured on the Sb_2Te_3 prepared on silicon oxide and aluminium oxides (4.9, 5.0, and 4.8 $\text{m}\Omega\text{ cm}$), consistently with their lower roughness (respect to $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3/\text{Si}$ films), a property that could be causally related to the homogeneity of the film and the orientation of its crystallites.

Compared with their As Deposited analogues, the two $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ - Substrate Annealing films were characterized by a slight increase of resistivity, due to their partially reduced structural order; whereas the $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3/\text{Si}$ - Substrate Annealing films, in agreement with their better crystallinity, showed lower resistivity. On the other hand, the resistivity of the $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3/\text{SiO}_2$ film increased considerably from 4.9 to 58 $\text{m}\Omega\text{ cm}$. In fact, not only it was found to be the less crystalline amongst all the samples, but also highly discontinuous. A common trend, however, is observed within the Post-Growth Annealing series of the films: all of them demonstrated a significant drop in resistivity, a result of their enhanced crystallinity and orientation.

Fig. 10. RT electrical resistivity of Sb_2Te_3 - As Deposited, Substrate Annealing, and Post-Growth Annealing grown on (green) Si(100), (blue) Si(111), (red) SiO_2 , (yellow) $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$, and (cyan) $\text{a-Al}_2\text{O}_3$.

Table 2. Electrical resistivity ($\text{m}\Omega\text{ cm}$) of the Sb_2Te_3 thin films.

	As Deposited	Substrate Annealing	Post-Growth Annealing
Si(111)	8.1	4.1	1.4
Si(100)	10.8	6.0	1.2
SiO ₂	4.9	58	1.6
a-Al ₂ O ₃	5.0	5.5	0.7
Al ₂ O ₃ (0001)	4.8	6.6	0.8

4. CONCLUSION

We grew by MOCVD a set of Sb₂Te₃ thin films exploiting the influence of substrates and thermal treatments. The tested substrates, amorphous and crystalline silicon- and aluminium-based materials, as well as the substrates annealing and post-growth processing protocols, were found crucial in directing the nature and the properties of the films.

As a trend, from the As Deposited to the Post-Growth Annealing series of films, the surface roughness and the granularity improved significantly with each substrate, apart from SiO₂.

Generally, the post-growth thermal annealing induced the crystallization of Sb₂Te₃ on each of the tested substrates and was also highly effective in influencing the in-plane and out-of-plane orientations of the film. In particular, the most intriguing results were obtained on the crystalline substrate Al₂O₃(0001), which promoted both an in-plane and out-of-plane orientation, as observed in a similar fashion on Si(111). The extent of the crystallization and ordering was first originated from the structural and morphological nature of the Sb₂Te₃ - Substrate Annealing, the parent films. Therefore, the choice of the substrate and the Substrate Annealing step appeared an essential pre-requisite.

Ultimately, the electrical resistivity was found qualitatively consistent with the overall structural features of the set of Sb₂Te₃ films, linking their structural and functional properties.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data.

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